

Managing Perioperative Glucose of Diabetic Patients

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Background

Diabetes Mellitus (DM)

- Most common endocrine disorder among surgical patients
- Stress-induced hyperglycemia can occur in patients without DM, but is more common in patients with DM
- Poor glycemic management increases morbidity and mortality (e.g., increased wound infection rates)

Class of 2021 Results

- Retrospective chart audit
- 100 patients with Type 2 DM in cases >2 hours at 13 hospitals
- 3% of patients had their blood glucose (BG) level checked

Class of 2022 Results

- Implemented a perioperative glycemic management protocol
- Educated anesthesia providers on BG management

Class of 2023 Results

- Retrospective chart audit
- 14% to 39% increase in perioperative BG monitoring after implementation of education; 20% of patients were being assessed every 2 hours

Problem & Purpose Statement

Problem: Failure to use a glycemic protocol contributes to suboptimal management of BG and increases the risk of poor patient outcomes

Purpose: Increase adherence to intraoperative glucose management protocol

Methods

Design: Qualitative descriptive study

Sample: 100 anesthesia providers

Setting: 245-bed Southern California Community Hospital

Goals: 20% response rate to barriers survey, Create an EMR reminder for perioperative BG checks

Conceptual Framework

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Barriers Survey Results

Q1 - What are potential barriers to appropriate perioperative hyperglycemic management? (Select all that apply)

Top 2 areas of concern identified:

1. Adequate access to supplies
2. Personnel-related issues

What Are Some Suggestions to Improve Perioperative Glucose Management?

The 4 main suggestions by anesthesia providers:

1. Easier access to glucometers/supplies
2. Better technology for BG assessment
3. EMR reminder availability
4. Streamlined glucometer control checks

What Are Potential Barriers to Appropriate Perioperative Hyperglycemic Management?

Top 3 specific barriers identified:

1. Available devices (glucometers)
2. Credentialing for anesthesia staff
3. Device quality control checks

Q4 - Would a reminder "pop-up" (clinical decision support tool) in HealthConnect be useful?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Yes	87.50%
2	No	12.50%

87.5% of anesthesia providers thought a reminder "pop-up" within the EMR would be useful

Discussion

- Lack of adequate supplies, lack of understanding of BG protocol, and lack of protocol implementation were barriers identified in the literature and in the survey
- Risk of patient hypoglycemia was not identified as a barrier in the survey

Recommendations

- Implement reminder "pop-up" within EMR
- Staff development
- Assign an anesthesia department champion
- Conduct a chart audit after implementation of reminder tool

Limitations

- Use of an online survey
- Self-reported answers
- Reproducibility
- Time constraints

Conclusion

The completion of this QI project has helped discover barriers and possible solutions that will improve glycemic management in patients with Type 2 DM receiving elective surgery.

References

